

Seismic Strengthening Design and Post-Intervention Capacity Evaluation of a Low-Rise Masonry Building

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Abstract

This study investigates the seismic strengthening of a three-storey unreinforced masonry building located in Tirana, Albania. The structure was originally built in the 1940s and later modified by adding an extra storey, which introduced stiffness irregularities and reduced lateral capacity, particularly in the transverse direction. Initial capacity assessments using spectrum-based analysis and nonlinear pushover procedures confirmed a high level of vulnerability. Based on these findings, a strengthening strategy was designed in accordance with Eurocode 8 – Part 3. The intervention scheme consists of new reinforced concrete (RC) columns at critical locations, RC jacketing of selected masonry walls, diaphragm strengthening, and foundation enhancement using tie-beams. Post-intervention pushover analyses were performed to quantify performance improvements. The results indicate significant gains in lateral resistance, overall stiffness, and deformation capacity. For a 95-year return period, the retrofitted building remains within the Damage Limitation state; for a 475-year event, it reaches the Significant Damage state without approaching Near Collapse. The adopted strengthening approach successfully mitigates the key deficiencies and complies with Eurocode 8 performance requirements. The findings also provide a practical reference for the retrofit of similar pre-code masonry structures in Tirana and other Albanian urban areas.

Keywords: Seismic retrofitting; Masonry buildings; Strengthening design; Eurocode 8; Pushover analysis; RC jacketing; CFRP.

1. Introduction

A large portion of Albania's low-rise masonry building stock dates from periods when seismic design provisions were either rudimentary or entirely absent. As a result, these structures frequently present heterogeneous materials, weak mortar, vertical and horizontal irregularities, and limited capacity for ductile behavior. The Mw 6.4 Durrës earthquake of 26 November 2019 highlighted these weaknesses, with many masonry buildings experiencing diagonal cracking, shear failure, pounding, and in some cases partial collapses.

The building discussed in this paper had already undergone a detailed seismic assessment using nonlinear static procedures and spectrum-based checks according to Eurocode 8. The analysis showed that the structure did not meet the target performance levels for either the 95-year or 475-year seismic events. Deficiencies were most evident

in the Y direction, where thin masonry walls, weak mortar and the added third storey produced a highly un-favorable lateral-load path.

In this context, the objective of the present work is to describe the strengthening strategy designed for the building and to evaluate the improvements achieved after the intervention. The intention is to provide a realistic and applicable strengthening approach for similar Albanian masonry structures, while remaining consistent with Eurocode-based assessment and design requirements.

2. Existing structural deficiencies

The primary structural deficiencies that were identified during the assessment are summarized in this chapter.

2.1 Weak Masonry Materials

The building consists of concrete-block masonry in the original two floors and clay brick masonry in the added upper level. Both materials showed relatively low compressive strength, and the mortar measured at around 2.5 MPa was well below the values typically required by Eurocode 6. This low mortar strength reduces the shear capacity of piers and weakens the bond between units; a condition commonly encountered in older Albanian masonry buildings.

Figure 1 depict the Photos from the building highlighting material deficiencies

Figure 1. Photos from the building highlighting material deficiencies

2.2 Stiffness Irregularity and Torsional Sensitivity

Variations in wall thickness, differences in materials between floors, and changes in storey height produced a vertical stiffness discontinuity. The construction of the third storey many years after the original building altered the structural system further, creating a non-uniform lateral-load path, see Figure 2.

- d) Enhancing global ductility and energy-dissipation capacity
- e) Improving diaphragm action to ensure better load distribution
- f) upgrading the foundation system to be compatible with the new vertical elements

Figure 4 depict the layout of the proposed strengthening interventions.

Figure 4. Layout of the Proposed Strengthening Interventions

4. Proposed strengthening interventions

Four major interventions are selected as the most effective and practical for this structure.

4.1 Reinforced Concrete Columns

New RC columns were introduced at locations where existing masonry piers were weak, discontinuous, or insufficient to carry lateral loads, see Figure 5. Their placement was chosen to contribute meaningfully to global stiffness, particularly in the Y direction. The columns are fully tied into upgraded foundations and floor diaphragms to ensure continuity.

Figure 5. Strengthening details for RC Columns

prevent differential settlement, while also improving connectivity between individual foundation units.

5. Post-intervention modelling and capacity comparison

After strengthening, the entire structure was re-modelled and re-analysed through nonlinear pushover analysis. Three-dimensional model of the retrofitted building are shown in the Figure 7.

Figure 7. Three-dimensional model of the retrofitted building

5.1 Pushover Curves After Strengthening

The strengthened building shows significantly improved capacity in both directions. The bilinear capacity parameters are summarized below:

Table 1. Mechanical properties of building materials

Building	Direction	Vmax	dt DL	dt SD	dt NC
Original	x	15360 kN	1.84cm	3.54cm	5.52cm
Original	y	6890 kN	0.88cm	1.12cm	1.54cm
Reinforced	x	21302 kN	1.52cm	3.52cm	5.78cm
Reinforced	y	16789 kN	1.31cm	2.12cm	4.92cm

The comparison between the pre- and post-intervention mechanical properties clearly demonstrates the effectiveness of the strengthening measures. The lateral strength in the Y direction, shows the most substantial improvement, increasing from 24.74% to 53.38% of the building weight, representing a capacity gain of over 100%. Similarly, the global stiffness of the structure increases by approximately 70% in both principal directions, rising from 8438 kN/m to 14014 kN/m in the X direction and from 7830 kN/m to 12914 kN/m in the Y direction. Ductility is also significantly enhanced, increasing from 2.54 to 3.75 in the X direction and from 3.78 to 4.73 in the Y direction, indicating a more favorable deformation capacity and improved seismic energy dissipation. These combined improvements confirm that the strengthened structure is more resistant, more ductile, and far better balanced in its seismic response compared to the original configuration.

5.2 Spectrum-Based Evaluation After Strengthening

Comparing the strengthened capacity curve with EC8 spectra:

- 95-year event ($a_g = 0.173g$): DL satisfied
- 475-year event ($a_g = 0.352g$): SD satisfied, NC not reached

This confirms EC8 compliance. Figure 8 depicts the capacity vs demand comparison of building pre and after retrofit

Figure 8. Capacity vs demand comparison of building pre and after retrofit

Before strengthening the structure reached Near Collapse but after strengthening, structure remains below SD, safely away from NC state.

6. Conclusion

A targeted seismic strengthening scheme was developed and applied to a vulnerable three-storey masonry building in Tirana. By combining RC columns, wall jacketing, diaphragm improvements and foundation upgrading, the intervention addressed the main weaknesses identified in the initial seismic assessment. The post-intervention pushover and spectrum-based analyses show that the upgraded structure now satisfies the performance requirements for both the 95-year and 475-year return-period earthquakes. The reduction in vulnerability, particularly in the Y direction, and the improved deformation capacity demonstrate the effectiveness of the adopted measures. The approach presented here can serve as a practical model for similar masonry buildings constructed prior to modern seismic codes in Albania.

Conflict of interests

The authors would like to confirm that there is no conflict of interests associated with this publication and there is no financial fund for this work that can affect the research outcomes.

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